

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Plan v1.0

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Summary

INGUMA Project aims to foster the development of bio-based materials and their acceptance by the public by relying on three main values sustainability, inclusion, and aesthetics - the values of the New European Bauhaus.

The value of sustainability will be tackled by developing different types of bio-based materials from raw materials derived from agriculture residues and secondary raw materials from wood processing. Various types of materials will be developed: functionalized fibers, insulation material based on mycelium, resin-free insulation material based on wood fibers, bio-based adhesive for plywood, low-formaldehyde plywood board, wooden sandwich panels, and growth media for plants. In addition, these materials will be integrated into insulation panels and vegetated roofs.

The sustainability and circularity of these materials and solutions will be ensured by applying environmental criteria and digital tools that will allow users to make decisions on the most sustainable solutions available. Additionally, the materials will be tested according to European and international standards, as a first step in the commercialization outside of Europe (Canada).

The value of inclusion will imply the design of co-creation laboratories that encourage collaboration among stakeholders, fostering transparent communication and generating innovative ideas. These labs will provide a platform for engagement and a structured process for stakeholders to contribute their insights and actively participate in the development of bio-based construction materials. This way, the acceptance of the developed materials, products and solutions by end-users and consumers will be maximized.

The value of aesthetics will be accomplished by co-designing and constructing a community house prototype in the rooftop of an experimental building (Derio, Spain) and as part of test houses (Savonlinna, Finland) that will use extensively the materials and products developed.

Executive Summary of the Deliverable

Communication, dissemination and exploitation - What impact can the INGUMA project achieve? How can visibility in all relevant channels, events and other areas support the valuable and sustainable development work of the project partners? Deliverable 6.1 - Communication, dissemination and exploitation planning is intended to provide an initial overview of precisely this.

The decisive tool for sustainable visibility is the visualisation of the project and the corresponding requirements for developments and objectives. On this basis, an innovative, modern and concise visual project communication was created in the first few months. The logo unifies all key requirements and will be the most important recognisable feature for the next 3.5 years.

On this basis and the initial strategic analysis of INGUMA's communication and dissemination potential, the development of a uniform communication mission is an elementary building block for the efficient use of resources and the definition of relevant goals:

Empowering the relevant audience to know, understand and promote the sustainable use of biomaterials to combat the global climate challenge.

The INGUMA communication & dissemination mission

Enabling potential target groups and stakeholders to understand, engage with and disseminate the all-important message of a sustainable construction sector over the course of the project is the generic goal of all communication and dissemination efforts.

Targetgroup	Needs/Interests	Partner Knowledge Transfer
Researcher & Developer	innovations, visions, science, unknown aspects, learnings, academic publications	TECNALIA,
Industry	processes, technologies, scalability, efficiency, business potentials	VTT, LUKE, TECNALIA, ARDI, BASK, GARN

Architects and building professionals	local and global regulations, Design, sustainable impact, environmental impact	ARDI, XAMK, NEORD
Policymakers and local authorities	local and global regulations, community aspects, environmental impact	ARDI, ATLAN
Citizens / End-Consumer	price, government benefits,	BASK, ARDI

The creative realisation is therefore geared precisely to this indicator. It is therefore extremely important not only to create the right content but also to know where to reach the target groups. For the INGUMA project, the following content and channels count as fundamental elements of all communication activities:

- **WEBSITE** (the central content hub - where interested parties can find all information and documents)
- **LinkedIn** (the most important social platform in terms of professional environments)
- **Instagram** (the architectural demand for sustainable construction and a high-quality design promises a significant impact on the relevant target group)
- **Standard communication material** (project brochure, poster, postcard, leaflet, templates)
- **Reporting partner activities**
- **Journalistic articles** on various topics
- **Material development** social media campaigns
- **Interviews** (written or video) with internal and external stakeholders
- **Various social media campaigns** (material development, end-products, demosite activities)
- **Instagram stories and reels** to reach a broad public
- **Various graphics/infographics** for explaining development and processes

Dissemination is also aimed at the relevant target groups and follows the overarching mission. It will achieve this sustainably through sister project collaborations, scientific papers, participation in events and conferences and the organisation of workshops and seminars.

The potential of exploitable results cannot yet be precisely validated at the time of publication of the deliverable. As of Month 6 of the project no changes in the project scope or exploitation goals of the partners have occurred or other progress communicated and the validity of the initial Exploitation Plan has been confirmed by all partners. As can be expected at this early stage, several gaps are seen in the Exploitation Plan, which will be clarified throughout the project and mainly through the two exploitation workshops.

Table of Acronyms

Abbreviation	Description
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
NGOs	Non-governmental organisations
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OI	Open Innovation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
SIP	Structural insulation panel
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
WP	Work Package

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1 General

The 1st edition **Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan** includes the detailed methodology to package the knowledge produced according to the targeted audiences needs and serves as an internal communication tool within the consortium.

The plan is divided into four main sections. The **Strategy and Concept** section forms the basis for all communication dissemination activities. Proven scientific methods from the field of communication and marketing were used to develop the findings. In the **Communication and Dissemination Activities** section, the plan shows all activities to be realised throughout the project phase. It should be noted that at the current stage of the project, some of the activities are ideas and may change as more knowledge is gained. The third section, **Timing of Activities**, shows the chronological order of all planned communication and dissemination activities in a table. The fourth section, **the 1st Map of Key Exploitable results**, gives a brief overview what could be the upcoming exploitable potentials of the INGUMA project. Basically, all activities in the project take the following objectives into account:

- Design and implement efficient communication and dissemination strategy directed at the target audience to raise awareness of the project.
- Identify the main stakeholders and ensure their engagement to increase the impact of the results achieved. - Participate in major European and international events and conferences.
- Develop an Exploitation Strategy in the form of a plan that complies with the EC contract and the Consortium Agreement signed between the partners.
- Protect the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) arising from the technological developments in the project in a manner that complies with the EC contract and the Consortium Agreement signed between the partners.

All Consortium members are committed to review the plan throughout the project and, together with G!E as work package leader (WP6), to adapt or redefine the strategy, concept and activities as necessary.

The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan will be updated again in month 24 of the project as Deliverable D 6.3. A detailed description and clustering with regard to stakeholder mapping is also provided in the update of the Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Plan.

2 Strategy and Concept

Biomaterials in the construction sector are not a real innovation. Nevertheless, their use and the acceptance of such materials is still rather low in all groups involved. The two most important tasks of the INGUMA project, **the development and use of biomaterials and their acceptance by the general public**, are the focus of the communication and dissemination strategy.

This means a task with multiple challenges for the activities in work package 6. In addition to the diversity of the topics, such as scientific research, material development, architectural application and urban transformation, it is above all the diversity of the potential target groups that defines the concept and the strategy of communication and dissemination. The individual needs and requirements of researchers, industry, architects, urban planners, policy makers and citizens must be taken into account in all areas of communication and dissemination.

Despite all the diversity, it is therefore extremely important for the development of the strategy to ensure consistency and recognisability in communication and dissemination. Without a uniform identity, it will not be possible to market the project sustainably and effectively.

Based on the two elementary development pillars of the INGUMA project, the innovative development of biomaterials and their practical application, the overarching communication and dissemination strategy has a unified mission:

Empowering the relevant audience to know, understand and promote the sustainable use of biomaterials to combat the global climate challenge.

The INGUMA communication & dissemination mission

The INGUMA project's overall development of communication and dissemination measures is based on this common understanding. The visual identity, the written identity and the creation of all content has the overarching ambition to fulfil this mission.

2.1 Visual Identity

The development of the visual identity of the INGUMA project is based on an analysis of the overall project requirements, the public project environment and the needs of the communicative addressees.

Colours, logo and design aim to unite the innovation, design and sustainability of the project and to reflect a certain uniqueness. The colour magenta as the INGUMA base colour has a clear signalling power and dynamism. In combination with the iconic representation of the house in which a tree stands, the logo unites all components of the project approach.

The lettering INGUMA is based on the FONT Silka. A design and graphically orientated FONT that reflects the creative element of architecture.

In general, the basic design, but also the design of the website and other communication materials is based on a modern graphic approach.

Figure 1 The INGUMA logo.

Figure 2 The INGUMA Font and colour palette.

Figure 3 Incorect use of the INGUMA logo.

2.2 Written Identity

The written identity has just as significant an influence on creation and perception as the visual identity. The standardised use of formulations and fixed terms not only enables the project to be communicated and marketed sustainably to the outside world. Standardising the language is also extremely important for internal understanding.

Full Project name: Reducing the footprint of consumer products through public dialogue and innovative bio-based materials.

Tagline: Fostering innovative bio-based materials in the construction sector.

Sentence: INGUMA aims to replace mineral and fossil-based construction materials with innovative bio-based materials and foster their acceptance through public dialogue.

Keywords: innovative bio-based materials, bio-based industry, building materials, green roof systems, insulation panels, agriculture, forestry, sustainability, inclusion, aesthetics

Why INGUMA?

The project name, INGUMA, is a nod to the Basque mythological god of dreams, who was believed to visit people's homes at night and torment them with nightmares, making it difficult to breathe.

Our interpretation of the myth is that the significant rise in atmospheric levels of CO₂ and its consequences for humankind is a genuine nightmare that requires us to take immediate action towards a massive decarbonisation of society.

The challenge:

Fostering the use of bio-based materials in the construction sector can improve the quality, comfort and performance of European buildings, and contribute to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions. To leverage this potential, focus must be placed on creating sustainably produced and long-lasting bio-based products.

Methodology:

INGUMA will develop, scale-up and demonstrate **fully recyclable bio-based materials for the construction sector**, and introduce a co-creation process to engage key stakeholders and foster public acceptance.

INGUMA will develop different types of bio-based materials from secondary raw materials derived from **agriculture** and **forestry**:

- bio-based adhesive;
- mycelia-based thermal insulation board;
- resin-free thermal insulation board;
- structural insulation panel;
- substrate for growing plant vegetation on green roofs.

These materials will be integrated into insulation panels and vegetated roofs.

INGUMA's approach contributes to the New European Bauhaus (NEB) initiative's values of **sustainability, inclusion and aesthetics**.

The **sustainability and circularity** of these materials and solutions will be ensured by applying environmental criteria and digital tools that allow users to make decisions on the most sustainable solutions available. Additionally, the materials will be tested according to European and international standards, as a first step towards their commercialisation outside of Europe (Canada).

Inclusion will be addressed through the design of co-creation laboratories that encourage collaboration among stakeholders, fostering transparent communication and generating innovative ideas. These labs will provide a platform for engagement and a structured process for stakeholders to share their insights and actively participate in the development of bio-based construction materials.

The value of **aesthetics** will be accomplished by co-designing and constructing a community house prototype in the rooftop of an experimental building in Derio (Spain) and as part of test houses in Savonlinna (Finland) that will extensively use the materials and products developed.

2.3 Target groups and relevant Stakeholder

As already described in the general section on the communication and dissemination strategy, the INGUMA project is aimed at very diverse target groups. In contrast to the classic marketing of a product, which can focus on a defined audience. This means that the uniformity of the project identity must go hand in hand with a high degree of individuality in the realisation of communication and dissemination content.

In addition to identifying the relevant target groups, it is very important from a communication perspective to precisely identify the respective needs and align the activities accordingly. Only if it is possible to attract the attention of the relevant target groups (see Figure 4 How communication turns interested parties into partners) is there a sustainable possibility of bringing the INGUMA mission to a successful conclusion.

Figure 4 How communication turns interested parties into partners. (source: Kate Jones @how_IC_it)

The aim is to develop as many potential interested parties as possible into commitment or even ownership through communication and dissemination activities. This should also take place sustainably beyond the end of the project.

2.4 Targetgroup overview

The following table 1 shows the relevant project target groups, their needs and the potential partner knowledge about the behaviour of the correspondingly defined group.

Table 1 Targetgroup overview.

Targetgroup	Needs/Interests	Partner Knowledge Transfer
Researcher & Developer	innovations, visions, science, unknown aspects, learnings, academic publications	TECNALIA,
Industry	processes, technologies, scalability, efficiency, business potentials	VTT, LUKE, TECNALIA, ARDI, BASK, GARN

Architects and building professionals	local and global regulations, Design, sustainable impact, environmental impact	ARDI, XAMK, NEORD
Policymakers and local authorities	local and global regulations, community aspects, environmental impact	ARDI, ATLAN
Citizens / End-Consumer	price, government benefits,	BASK, ARDI

2.5 Stakeholder Mapping

In addition to analysing and defining target groups and developing relevant content, the involvement of stakeholders is the second important pillar in the alignment of communication and dissemination activities. The identification and detailed mapping of key stakeholders and clusters of people who will provide valuable input during the project period and have a potential interest in the development will be one of the most important tasks over the next 6 months. A detailed mapping as a strategic basis for the sustainable involvement of potential stakeholders will be based on the first analysis from work package 2 with regard to task 2.1 - Stakeholder Engagement. The stakeholders along the development chain listed in the following table 2 provide an initial orientation.

Table 2 First analysis of potential stakeholders regarding the research of WP2 (table published in D2.1).

Value chain activity	Type of stakeholders
Raw materials	Farmers, Foresters, Mechanical wood processing industry (e.g. saw mills), Mushroom growers
Finance and funding	Private sector financing (banks, investors, venture capitalist, hedge funds, etc.), Public sector funding (R&I support, subsidies and loans for companies, affordable housing support, etc.)
Research and education	Universities, Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs), Vocational education and training
Planning, design, and commissioning	Architects, Engineering companies, Urban planners and developers, Local administration, Exterior and interior designers
Construction materials and equipment industry	Material manufacturing companies, Product manufacturers, Solution providers, Equipment, machinery, and tools suppliers
Logistics and distribution	Commercialisers, Distributors, Logistics companies
Construction industry	Construction companies, Landscape construction companies, Industrialised construction, Builders, Sub-contractors of construction companies
Property market	Real estate companies, Building developers, Building companies, Building and house owners
Operation, maintenance, and renovation	Maintenance companies, Building managers, Individuals
End-of-life	Demolition companies, Decommissioning and waste management companies

Policy, regulation and standardisation	<p>Policymakers in different governance levels (EU, national, regional, local), Public administration, Authorities involved in regulation, Standardisation bodies, Certification bodies, Label organisations</p>
Industry associations	<p>Clusters, Industrial associations</p>
End-users	<p>Building and house residents, Building and house owners, Public building owners and users, Building managers, Housing, properties and residential associations</p>
Others	<p>Construction workers, Insurance agents, Students, Other industries, Hardware stores, Retail stores selling construction materials or furniture, Trade fair organisers, Communication and media, Influencers, Non-governmental organisations</p>

As already mentioned in the general introduction to this deliverable, a detailed report on the task of stakeholder mapping is provided in the following report - deliverable 6.3.

3 Communication and Dissemination Action

Communication and dissemination actions will contribute to raising awareness of the project and its results amongst relevant stakeholders, as well as amongst society more broadly to communicate the benefits of publicly funded research. Communication supports dissemination, making people aware of the project and results and by its nature it targets a wide number of stakeholders. Communication will also be used to engage stakeholders and inform them on project developments. All communications actions will target all relevant stakeholders.

Based on the overarching communication mission, communication activities will be focused on relevant tasks and channels. In doing so, it should be taken into account that too much diversity in the implementation and use of too many digital distribution channels will not lead to the desired result.

With regard to the use of the project's own channels, INGUMA is therefore focussing on three important building blocks:

- **WEBSITE** (the central content hub - where interested parties can find all information and documents)
- **LinkedIn** (the most important social platform in terms of professional environments)
- **Instagram** (the architectural demand for sustainable construction and a high-quality design promises a significant impact on the relevant target group)

In addition, INGUMA uses YouTube as a central video database. The use of the video portal also has a technical implication. The playout of the videos on the WordPress website depends on this.

3.1 Communication Action

Communication and its content are decisively characterised by the following content formats:

- **Standard communication material** (project brochure, poster, postcard, leaflet, templates)
- **Reporting partner activities**
- **Journalistic articles** on various topics
- **Material development** social media campaigns
- **Interviews** (written or video) with internal and external stakeholders
- **Various social media campaigns** (material development, end-products, demosite activities)
- **Instagram stories and reels** to reach a broad public
- **Various graphics/infographics** for explaining development and processes

3.1.1 Website

The INGUMA website is the central content hub of the project. This is where all the content produced for the potential audience is organised and stored. The website has been developed and implemented on the widely known WordPress backend. This enables the responsible

administrators of Greenovate!Europe to update the content efficiently and sustainably without the need for additional programming.

The visual and content concept of the website is based on the visual identity of the project and combines all the requirements from the overarching definition of the corresponding objectives. An important communicative factor in this case is also the visual language. Here it is important that the project partners reliably provide appropriate material in order to visualise the activities in a graphically appealing way.

The project content is structured online using the following page layout:

- **Main page** - general project information, news, demo locations and partners (permanent update)
- **The project** - detailed overview of all project information (static content)
- **The developments** - all information on material development and the test cases (static page)
- **News and downloads** - the project blog and the INGUMA document repository (permanent update)
- **About us** - contact persons and partner overview (static content)

<https://www.inguma-biobased.eu/>

Figure 5 INGUMA landing page.

Figure 6 INGUMA website structure.

Figure 7 INGUMA website extended version THE PROJECT.

Figure 8 INGUMA website extended version DEVELOPMENTS & ABOUT US.

3.1.2 Social Media

Two central social media will be used in the INGUMA project. As described above, LinkedIn and Instagram are the channels with the greatest expected potential in terms of the relevant communication and dissemination objectives.

Communication in social networks is so important because the way in which digital content is consumed has changed massively in recent years. Whereas 5 years ago the project's own channel, the website, was of central importance, today it is the preferred communication channel of the relevant target groups.

For this reason, the entire creation and production of content will be aligned with the Social Media 1st concept. If the audience prefers to consume their content on LinkedIn and Instagram, the communication will be aligned with this.

Figure 9 INGUMA LinkedIn posts.

3.1.3 Demosite Videos

One of the most important communication activities in the 2nd half of the project will be the creation of 2 DemoSite videos. These videos will be realised in a classic documentation team format and meet the requirements of modern audiovisual science communication.

The aim of the videos is to reach consumers and local authorities with the most important messages. Particularly in the final phase of the project, the two videos will play a decisive strategic communication role. They are intended to bring the development and realisation of the INGUMA project to life.

3.1.4 Partner Action

For the area of communication, it is of great importance that all project partners support this work package. This is not just about regular updates on local activities (a monthly WP6 meeting will start in the second half of 2024 to exchange information with all partners), but above all about their own initiatives. The communication of partner-specific tasks in the corresponding local networks has an enormous influence on the reach of all communication.

It is important that the partners not only disseminate overarching information in their digital channels. Rather, it is important, especially at the beginning of the project, to create and use your own communication materials based on the developed project identity. G!E supports all partners in this task. The following table 3 shows the partner's person months that they should use for communication and dissemination.

Table 3 Partner resources for communication & dissemination.

Partner	PM
TECN	25
TCERT	-
GARN	2
CHIMAR	2
ORLO	2
IA+B	2
NEORD	2
VTT	3.5
LUKE	2
IW	2
FNR	2
ARDI	2

G!E	18
ATLAN	31
XAMK	2
BASK	2
LAVAL	2

3.2 Dissemination Action

3.2.1 Collaboration with Sisterprojects

For sustainable and efficient dissemination, INGUMA works closely together with its flagship projects. The aim is to share knowledge transfer and findings in all areas of research, development and implementation. This should also happen in the area of communication and dissemination.

Above all, the reach of potential target groups with the various separate but also joint activities is an elementary advantage. Another goal is the efficient utilisation of resources and different potentials and experiences.

In addition to joint communication activities (see Figure 5), joint dissemination ideas are already being planned, including joint participation in conferences and events or the realisation of webinars or workshops. There is also potential in joint work on policy briefing and recommendation.

Figure 10 LinkedIn post sister project BIOBUILD collaboration.

3.2.2 Events and Conferences

With regard to the important task of disseminating the project content and, in the further course, the project results and learnings, the relevant partners will participate in various (at least 20) conferences and events. The aim is to prepare and present content that is specifically relevant to the target group to be reached. Participation will be accompanied and supported by publication in the social media and corresponding communication materials. Table 4 below shows all the conferences currently under consideration and the corresponding responsibilities of the project partners.

Table 4 Conferences & Events.

Conferences & Events	Related Partner
Drivers for Wood Construction	NEORD, IA+B
European Biomass Conference & Exhibition	VTT
European Wood-based Panel Symposium	GARN, FNR
European Workshop on Lignocellulosics and Pulp	ORLO
Ibero-Latin American Congress of Wood in Construction	LAVAL
InnovaWood General Assembly	XAMK, BASK
International Conference on Renewable Resources & Biorefineries	TECNALIA, VTT
International Mass Timber Conference	TBD.
International Wood BioEconomy-Forum	ATLANTIS
Nordic Wood Biorefinery Conference	LUKE, VTT, ORLO
SWST Convention	TBD.
World Conference on Timber Engineering	ORLO
World Wood Day Online Symposium	TECNALIA, BASK, NEORD
Woodrise Congress	TBD.

3.2.3 Zenodo

In addition to publishing all public documents and materials on the project website, INGUMA uses the European content platform Zenodo to publish and disseminate results and important information. The aim of integrating Zenodo is to reach the target groups in the European project environment. Another decisive advantage is the unlimited availability far beyond the end of the project.

<https://zenodo.org/communities/inguma>

3.2.4 Scientific Publications

In total, at least 8 different scientific papers will be produced and published during the project period. These must be published in appropriate journals. The following journals and scientific publications have already been identified:

Bioresource Technology; Biotechnology & Bioengineering; Building and Environmental; Energy & Buildings; European Journal of Wood & Wood Products; Industrial Crops & Products; Journal of Applied Polymer Science; Journal of Chemical Technology & Biotechnology; Journal of Cleaner Production; Journal of Wood Chemistry & Technology; Processes; Resources; Sustainability; Wood Science & Technology.

The preparation of the scientific papers is the responsibility of the following partners:

3.2.5 Final Event

A final conference will be held (Brussels, or suitable industry forum) to bring final results and policy messages to end-users. At the current stage of the project, it is not yet possible to communicate any sustainable facts on this task. A detailed description is planned for the update in month 24.

3.3 Measurement and KPI's

The following analytical tools will be used in the INGUMA project to ensure a transparent overview of all communication activities, especially digital ones:

- Website (Matomo - 100% compliant with European GDPR requirements)
- LinkedIn (platform's own analysis tool)
- Instagram (platform's own analysis tool)
- Zenodo (platform's own analysis tool)
- YouTube (platform's own analysis tool)

Table 5 Communication & Dissemination KPI's.

TASK	KPI
Brochure	1
Roll-Up Banner	1
Social Media Visuals	1
Standard Presentation	1
Website	20.000 Page Views
Press Releases	8
Interviews	8
Journalistic Articles	8

Social Media	2.000 Followers
Scientific and Technical Publications	8
Presentation in Conferences	20
Policy and Brief Recommendations	1
End-Product Social Media Campaign (incl infographics)	6
Webinars	3 (200 views)
Demo Videos	2
Fact Sheets	6

3.4 Coming Next

Over the next 18 months, the communication and dissemination work will focus mainly on publicising the project in general and disseminating the material development. The main focus will be on target groups and stakeholders from the fields of research and development as well as industry as a focus audience.

Therefore, the aim in the following weeks and months is, among other things, to push corresponding communication activities:

- General brochure
- Roll-up banner
- information regarding the material development
- Social media campaign on material development
- update of the website
- 4 journalistic articles and outreach activities
- start of Instagram communication
- production of first factsheets
- support for first steps DemoSite activities
- Posters, leaflets and postcards for conferences and events
- Stakeholder workshop communication

The activities in the area of dissemination focus on the following tasks:

- publicising developments and innovations at relevant conferences and events
- collaborations with our sister project Biobuild
- submission of 4 scientific publications
- application of all available public papers of the project

4 Timing of Activities

Table 5 below shows all implemented and currently planned activities of the INGUMA project:

Table 6 Timing of activities.

Projekt Month	Month	Content/Activity	Channel
2024			
M1	January	Kick-Off Meeting	General
M2	February	Start Social Media Activities	LinkedIn
M3	March	Social Media activities PPT Template Word Template Visual Identity	LinkedIn
M4	April	Social Media activities	LinkedIn
M5	May	Social Media activities Website Launch (1 st landing page)	LinkedIn Website
M6	June	Social Media activities 1 st sister project collaboration announcement	LinkedIn LinkedIn
M7	July	Website extension (whole content) 1 st website articles	Website Website
M8	August	Brochure Roll-Up 1 st Press Release Social Media activities	General General Outreach LinkedIn
M9	September	Start Instagram communication 1 st Social Media Material Development Campaign Website Article	Instagram, LinkedIn Website

M10	October	Conference participation (tbd.) Sister Project Collaboration 1 st Interview	All channels
M11	November	Postcard Stakeholder Involvement 1 st Journalistic Article	General Website Outreach
M12	December	2 nd Social Media Material Development Campaign	LinkedIn, Instagram
2025			
M13	January	2 nd Interview	All Channels
M14	February	Website Update	Website, LinkedIn
M15	March	2 nd Journalistic Article	Outreach
M16	April	3 rd Social Media Material Development Campaign	LinkedIn, Instagram
M17	May	3 rd Interview	Website, LinkedIn
M18	June	2 nd Press Release	Outreach
M19	July	3 rd Journalistic Article	Outreach
M20	August		
M21	September	4 th Social Media Material Development Campaign	LinkedIn, Instagram
M22	October		
M23	November	4 th Journalistic Article	Outreach
M24	December		
2026			
	Januar	4 th Interview	Website, LinkedIn

5 Exploitation Map

This report constitutes part of the first preliminary version of deliverable D6.1: Communication, Exploitation and Communication Plan. The Preliminary Exploitation Plan is a working document which will be periodically updated as the technological developments and results of the project are completed.

A draft Exploitation Plan was prepared at the proposal stage. The document presents the latest version of the exploitation plan, and particularly the Summary Exploitation Plan Table. The Exploitation Plan Table is based on the initial version developed during the project proposal stage and the results of the first exploitation Workshop which took place in June 2024. In particular, the list of key exploitable results as well as preferred IPR strategies and exploitation routes are presented.

Several aspects were discussed during the exploitation workshop, with a focus on the list of commercially exploitable results and foreseen TRLs for each and discussion on the roles that each partner intends to have in the exploitation of project results after the end of the project.

The Exploitation Plan will be updated periodically throughout the project. At a later stage, techno-economic and market readiness aspects will be consolidated, to identify the main barriers and opportunities for each KER and to assess their potential for exploitation and replication. These results, together with stakeholder readiness assessment and an analysis of the partners' interests, capacities and investment commitments, will act as the main drivers for developing the final version of the INGUMA Exploitation Strategy.

5.1 Draft Exploitation Plan

As of Month 6 of the project no changes in the project scope or exploitation goals of the partners have occurred or other progress communicated and the validity of the initial Exploitation Plan has been confirmed by all partners. The Draft Exploitation Plan, as prepared by Month 6 of the project is presented in Table 7.

As can be expected at this early stage, several gaps are seen in the Exploitation Plan, which will be clarified throughout the project and mainly through the two exploitation workshops. An important aspect to be considered in developing a workable Exploitation Plan concerns the agreement between all partners of an Action Plan to be followed after the end of the project. Special emphasis will therefore be given to defining IP and terms of cooperation with emphasis to allocation of exploitation/ commercialization rights, determining the level of interest of partners and securing commitments for participating to the activities needed after the project and for contributing to the required budgetary and resource investments.

Table 7 Draft Exploitation Action Plan.

Key exploitable results	Partners generating	target audience	Potential end users/ Partners	Exploitation Route	Month	IPR Strategy
Enzymatic treatments	VTT	Bio - Feedstock producers and fibre board manufacturers	VTT	Knowledge-transfer to the industry, Licensing	M21	Patent

Fibre processing via reactive extrusion	VTT	Bio - Feedstock producers, fibre board manufacturers	VTT	Knowledge-transfer to the industry, Licensing	M21	Patent
Bio-based adhesive	CHIMAR	Plywood manufacturers	CHIMAR GARN	Commercialization by sales representatives	M21	Patent
Green Plywood	GARN, CHIMAR	Construction companies	CHIMAR GARN	Integration in further products/processes, manufacture and sell the solutions	M21	Trade secret
Resin-free woodfibre insulation board	TECN	Insulation manufacturers, equipment manufacturers	TECN	Creation of a spin-off	M36	Patent
Mycelia-based insulation board	LUKE	Insulation manufacturers	LUKE	Knowledge-transfer to the stake holders and industry	M36	Patent or trade secret
Growing media for green roofs	LUKE	Construction companies, growth media manufactures	LUKE, NEORD	Knowledge-transfer to the stake holders and industry	M36	Patent or trade secret
Green roof	NEORD	Construction companies	NEORD	Knowledge-transfer to the industry	M48	Trade secret
Concept of community house	IA+B	Construction companies	IA+B	Consultancy services on use of results	M48	Trade secret

5.2 Exploitation Strategy

5.2.1 IP Management

For the purposes of the project, background is defined as “*data, know-how or information, whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible) including any rights such as IPR that is held by the beneficiary before they acceded to the Agreement, and which is needed to implement the action or exploit the results*”.

Because of the need to use background material, access rights have to be granted at the beginning, in principle. The partners have already identified, and agreed amongst them, on the Background for the project. Stemming from the above definition, background can take many forms, such as:

- Intellectual property rights,
- Confidential information and databases, trade secrets and know-how
- Tangible assets

A list of the relevant background IP from each partner has been defined at the proposal stage and has also been included in the CA.

5.2.2 Foreground

The project foresees several exploitable results, which will need to be protected via patent or other mechanism. An initial list of expected exploitable results, ownership and protection strategy is already stated in the Draft Exploitation Plan. The draft Plan is intended to facilitate discussions for further defining and detailing the project results, ownership, and protection strategy. It will also be

important for the INGUMA consortium to agree on a collaboration strategy, which will not only enable but encourage the exploitation / replication of results by partners who are not owners but are interested to use the project results.

Project results will in general be owned by the partners that were involved in their development including any rights attached to it, such as patents or intellectual property rights. Should more than one partner be involved in this development, the results will be jointly owned, unless otherwise agreed by the involved parties. The project manager will maintain an overview of all the results generated in the project and will oversee any necessary IPR protection strategies. No results will be publicly disseminated/communicated before they have been formally evaluated by the result owner and Project Coordinator. The IPR Plan as of Month 6 is presented in Table 8.

Table 8 IP background brought to INGUMA and expected foreground generated in INGUMA per partner.

Partner	Background IP	Foreground IP
TECN	Patent PCT/EP2015/076861 "Porous cellulosic materials and processes for their preparation" / TRACEBLOCK (Software registered at USCO N° TXU 2-105-160): Blockchainbased platform that traces assets along entire supply chains.	Up-scaling of the manufacture of the resin-free insulator Application of TRACEBLOCK to bio-based construction value chain.
GARN	Know-how on plywood and SIP manufacturing	Design of fully circular SIP
CHIMAR	Synthesis and industrial production of bio-based adhesives as well as on their application in wood-based panels manufacture. Patent WO 00/23490 (Bonding Resins) concerned the production of phenolic adhesives using natural phenolic materials.	Progress on (a) the production of bio-based adhesives using naturally derived materials (organic acids, carbohydrates, proteins and various crosslinkers) and (b) their application in plywood manufacture.
ORLO	Know-how on turnkey projects for the paper sector	Design of a pilot plant for the manufacture of the resin-free insulator
NEORD	Know-how on green spaces, landscaping & green roofs	Design of green roofs with innovative substrates
VTT	Know-how on "Enzymatic treatment of fibres in twin-screw extruder". Trade secret "optimal configuration of the screw for enzymatic biomass processing".	Optimal enzyme cocktail for reducing energy consumption in processing of agricultural residues.
LUKE	Know-how on mycelial insulation materials and side stream based growing media for green roofs	Upscaling of mycelial insulation materials and substrates

Lastly it needs to be noted that the project applies an open science approach. The data management therefore needs to incorporate specific clauses for defining confidential and patentable information to ensure that there will not be any disclosure of information which could undermine the confidentiality requirements and the interests of the affected partners. For this purpose, the data management plan will need to define also the level of access of each deliverable, or parts thereof. The Exploitation Plan already presents the initial aspirations of the partners regarding foreground IP. This Plan will be subject to further consultations during the project such that an IPR plan including commercialization rights agreements is agreed by all partners.

6 Conclusion

The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan v1.0 in month 6 clearly shows where the challenges of the tasks in work package 6 of the INGUMA project lie.

Despite a unified mission to inform and educate all target groups about the current state of construction possibilities with biomaterials and to increase the acceptance of sustainable building concepts, the diversity of target group needs is a decisive factor in INGUMA communication and dissemination.

On the one hand, the diversity of target group needs requires a high degree of flexibility; on the other hand, the uniform message should be understood across all target groups and ideally multiplied by the recipients.

The next 12 months will show whether the conceptual, strategic and content-related decisions were made correctly. By actively involving stakeholders from the respective target groups, you will have the opportunity to reflect on some of the measures and correct them if necessary. In addition, the permanent measurement of digital publications enables us to act quickly and optimise the communicated content.

With regard to the upcoming collaboration with relevant stakeholders from the defined target groups, a precise plan of the relevant stakeholders and their potential for further project collaboration will be developed in the coming months.

A clear picture should also emerge for the potential of the Exploitable Results by the time of the update in month 24.